

SELF-ASSESSMENT AS A PROCESS OF PERSONAL FORMATION IN ADOLESCENT STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this article, self-assessment in adolescent students is interpreted as a process of personal formation. Also, it is thought that self-evaluation and self-awareness of adolescent students have a moral-emotional nature.*

Keywords: *adolescent, adolescence, self-esteem, adequate self-esteem, individual development, personal qualities, adequacy, activity, self perception, objective assessment.*

Adequate self-esteem of adolescent students is preserved for a long time, which allows to create some conditions for its change in case of violation of its adequacy and positivity. Adequate self-evaluation, that is, the process of forming a clear, stable attitude of the subject towards himself, is directly related to the problems of education, upbringing and development.

In the encyclopedia of pedagogy [1], it is interpreted as "Adequacy" (Latin *adaequatus* - equal, suitable, exactly one, similar) - in the theory of knowledge, the selection of the properties and relations of things and events in accordance with their objective content." The human mind adequately reflects objective existence on the basis of social practice. The level of adequacy, i.e., the question of the accuracy, depth and completeness of the reflection of the object, depends on the problem of the relationship between relative and absolute truths and the correctness of knowledge, the criterion[1; p. 64].

Self-assessment is a process of personal formation that goes through certain stages of its own development. The main conflict, which is the source and driving force for the development of objective self-evaluation, arises from the ideas about oneself and from other people in the form of approval or encouragement, signs of success or failure. embodies the contradictions between self-evaluation. They, in turn, set new goals and tasks for a person, determine the emergence of new high-level needs, and therefore perform a developmental function. In general, the mechanism of adequate self-evaluation can be expressed as follows: self-knowledge comes from knowing one's own relationship with the outside world, other people, their relationships, etc.

At the initial stages of self-awareness, only the external, visible side of one's behavior is realized. Later, feelings, interests, aspirations, system of various motives, etc. gradually enter the field of self-knowledge. Knowing the characteristics of other people, their external manifestations in their activities and behavior, the attitude of others to him, a person interprets and correlates these individual aspects of objective knowledge, as a result of which he evaluates himself. forms. Thus, self-assessment is a specific result of self-awareness and reflects the level of formation of a person at a certain stage of development [2].

A comparative analysis of the functioning of the emotional and cognitive components of self-esteem allows us to come to the following conclusion: the interaction of the emotional and cognitive components of self-esteem in older preschool children is not clear, linear .

Adequate self-assessment allows the subject to have a critical attitude towards himself, to correctly connect his strengths with tasks of various difficulties and the demands of others. Negative self-esteem - a low level of self-esteem, a sense of self-awareness, forms a negative attitude towards a person.

In self-evaluation, the image of the real "I" should be compared with the image of the ideal "I", that is, with the idea of what kind of person I want to be. In this case, the high degree of compatibility of the real person with the ideal is an important indicator of pedagogical and psychological development [3].

In the process of adequate self-evaluation, the main components, for example, goal setting, ideal self-reflection, should be sufficiently formed.

There are the following types of self-assessment: general and personal. Personal self-evaluation is formed due to the development and development of such components as "I am ideal", "reflection" and "goal setting" in its composition. The ideal of "I" serves as a source of formation of human values, reveals ideas about one's future. The inconsistency between real and ideal qualities is considered as a kind of contradiction between "ideal-I" and "real-I".

The personality of the adolescent student is more independent from the influence of adults. By this time, his relationships with others will expand and become more complicated. This allows for a more complete and deep self-awareness and appreciation [4].

A teenager develops under the influence of social relations and evaluations of others. Every new experience, new knowledge, skill acquired by a teenager is evaluated by others. As a result, the need to evaluate his actions, to confirm the truth or wrongness of the truth that he understands begins to form content.

In adolescent students, independent self-evaluation appears in external evaluation in connection with the elements of self-image. This is a unique process of recognition in the period of life, which eliminates the instability of ideas about oneself.

A significant change in the development of the personality of a student at the age of a teenager is the transition from the assessment of the subject of another person to the assessment of his personal characteristics and his own internal state.

Observations and evaluative comments of adolescent students to their peers are carried out without distinguishing any individual, characteristic features. Their assessment will have a general, undifferentiated character. For example, "trustworthy", "bad", "smart", "incompetent".

Self-evaluation and self-awareness in adolescent students have a moral-emotional character. Among the surrounding adults, children who feel mutual respect, trust, and love receive the brightest positive evaluation. As a result of comparing the self-assessment of a student in various activities, one can see his objectivity ("high self-assessment", "adequate assessment", "low self-assessment") [5].

The accuracy of self-assessment of adolescent students largely depends on the specificity of the activity, the visibility of the results, knowledge of their own skills and experience in evaluating them, and the real experience in this field. The level of mastery of assessment criteria is determined by the level of self-assessment. Thus, it is easier for teenagers to evaluate their position in the system of personal relationships than to evaluate their own thinking on a certain moral topic. It was found that the status of the adolescent student, his position in the class also affects his adequate self-evaluation.

Adolescent students maintain a general positive self-esteem based on the unselfish kindness and care of others. It helps to strengthen the ideas of the students of the teenage age about their abilities. The expansion of the types of activities mastered by a teenager leads to the formation of a clear and reliable self-assessment, which indicates his reaction to the success of a particular action.

Adolescence is characterized by the separation of a person's assessment of himself from the assessment given by others. Adolescent student's awareness of the limits of their powers occurs not only in communication with others, but also in their own practical experience; Adolescents who have overestimated or underestimated self-concepts are sensitive to and easily swayed by the evaluative influence of others.

Under the influence of evaluation, a certain attitude towards others appears, and at the same time, the ability to see oneself through their eyes develops. A teenager's ability to analyze the results of his activity directly depends on the ability to analyze the results achieved by other peers. Thus, communication with peers develops the ability to evaluate another person, which in turn stimulates the development of self-evaluation. It represents the adolescent's attitude towards himself compared to other people.

Peer evaluations are important for teenage students. During this period, a teenager overestimates his abilities, knows little about his personal qualities and cognitive abilities, often confuses specific achievements with high personal evaluation.

The analysis of literary sources devoted to the problem of self-assessment and self-development of a person allows us to identify a number of peculiarities for students of adolescent age:

1. Self-evaluation of a student of adolescent age is an unstable, situational phenomenon.
2. During this period, the dynamics of self-assessment skills formation in the student is carried out in three main directions:
 - a) an increase in the number of personal qualities and activities evaluated by him;
 - b) transition from external self-esteem to internal, personal self-evaluation;
 - c) strengthening of adequate self-assessment over time. This is manifested both in elementary self-analysis of his previous actions and in predicting his future.
3. The mechanism of development of self-assessment skills in adolescent students is manifested as follows:
 - a) through special types of generalized assessments;
 - b) the ability to self-assess based on information about the quality of results in solving specific problems by evaluating adults (parents, grandparents, teachers) who are important in the adolescent's life, and then peers development.
4. The most adequate personal self-assessment in adolescent students is generally recognized as overestimated in comparison with the realistic self-awareness characteristic of adults.
5. Self-assessment of a student of adolescent age is characterized by the following: integrity; lack of objectivity and validity; the existence of an overestimated level of claims.

Therefore, the formation of personality is a complex and long-lasting process. This continues under the direct influence of others, first of all, adults. Adolescence is crucial in the genesis of self-esteem in the early stages of personality formation. Without knowing the

characteristics of adolescence, it is difficult to correctly react to their actions, choose the appropriate reprimand or encouragement, and purposefully manage education.

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